

Application of herbicide lethality in hybrid rice

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With improved seed production technology and parental out-crossing traits, hybrid rice seed production yield has increased from hundreds of kilograms per hectare to a national average of 2.5 t ha⁻¹ during the last three decades in China. However, current seed production protocols are based on a technology established 30 years ago—female and male parents are separately transplanted in different rows at a certain ratio and are harvested separately. The complexity of seed production has become a limiting factor for wide-scale adoption of hybrid rice as more labor is consumed and purity control and mechanical operations are difficult.

In 1984, Norin 8M, a mutant from japonica rice variety Norin 8, was found to be lethally susceptible to bentazone (3-isopropyl-1H-benzo-2,1,3-thiadiazine-4(3H)-ketone-2,2-dioxide), which is an ingredient of herbicides such as “basagran,” “bentazone,” and others that are used widely in rice fields for weed control. The discovery of bentazone lethality, which was genetically controlled by a pair of recessive genes, opened the path for an innovative system of hybrid rice seed production. The key approach is to integrate the lethality trait into restorer lines, which have the same days to flowering as the cytoplasmic male sterile (CMS) lines, so that seeds of both female and male parents can be blended, planted, or transplanted

together. After pollination, the herbicide bentazone is sprayed in the field to eliminate the male plants, leaving CMS plants bearing hybrid seeds that can be bulk-harvested. This technology simplifies the operation of seed production, employs less labor, and is adaptable to mechanical seed production on a large scale, besides increasing hybrid seed yield and purity. After 21 seasons in 10 years of breeding, we successfully developed many CMS restorer lines with bentazone lethality and with different maturities to synchronize planting of various CMS lines. Heterotic hybrids were developed using these restorer lines and were applied to commercial production.

The donor parent of the lethality trait was a mutant line contributed by Dr. G. Takeda), Norin 8M, which is lethally susceptible to bentazone. A typical japonica variety, it was used to cross with many indica restorer lines to develop restorer lines with an indica genetic background having bentazone lethality. It has the same days to flowering as that of the CMS female parent. Pedigree and backcross breeding were used. The herbicide dose study was first carried out to select the best herbicide rate that would let plants show obvious but limited damage from the chemical and would let them survive until seed harvest. The herbicide used, made by Jiansu Lulilai Co. Ltd., China, was bentazone 25% aqua. (The normal dosage recommended

by the manufacturer for rice is 3,000–6,000 mL ha⁻¹.) Experiments showed that, at heading stage, application of 600 mL ha⁻¹ of bentazone showed no damage to plants; with 900 mL ha⁻¹, plants had minor damage but recovered within 10 d after herbicide spraying. However, with 1,200–1,800 mL ha⁻¹, the plants showed obvious damage 7 d after spraying and the panicles died after 10 d. At a dose of 2,700–3,600 mL ha⁻¹, obvious damage was observed in the plants by the 4th day after spraying and the whole plant died 10 d after spraying.

In the course of breeding, 900 mL bentazone ha⁻¹ was applied to screen plants with susceptibility at the panicle initiation stage in every breeding generation from F₂. Selection on the basis of phenotype was started on the 7th day after herbicide treatment. Herbicide susceptibility, along with other agronomic traits, was selected following the same selection criteria used in a general restorer line breeding program. The trait days to flowering was specifically noted because of the required flowering synchronization with female parents. Different CMS lines were planted along with R lines to provide a reference of days to flowering. The selected R lines were harvested as single plants, advanced to the next generation, and then testcrossed with various CMS lines to make hybrids for evaluation of restoration ability, combining ability, and yield (heterosis). Table 1 shows

the characteristics of the selected R lines used in the herbicide dosage study.

The selected hybrid varieties with high yield potential and acceptable quality were advanced to provincial or national yield trials and tested for commercial hybrid seed production. Many restorer lines with bentazone lethality in various indica genetic backgrounds and related commercial hybrids have now been developed. One of the good performers, hybrid “Green Rice # 5”, has gained nationwide ac-

ceptance and is being commercialized. In a farmer’s yield trial in 2004, it produced 11.45 t ha⁻¹ and outyielded, by 1.52 t ha⁻¹, the best hybrid check, Shanyou 63, the most widely grown hybrid in China. It had a 15.3% yield advantage but the same maturity.

In a 2004 seed production study, two systems—conventional seed production (row ratio of 1 male: 5 females, separate transplanting) and mixed transplanting (seed ratio of 1 male: 5 females, mixed transplanting)—were evaluated. Results showed that the mixed method produced 2.0 t ha⁻¹ more hybrid seeds than

did the conventional method, with a 42.6% yield increase (Table 2). All yield components in the mixed method had different levels of increase, but the most significant increase was in seed set rate, which was 25% higher than in the conventional method.

By using molecular marker technology, the lethality trait has been mapped in the rice genome. In future development of lines with bentazone lethality, it will be very helpful to apply market-assisted selection to speed up and increase the accuracy of the selection process.

Table 1. Lethality of R line 2E06, Hefei, 2004.

Herbicide dose (mL ha ⁻¹)	Fertile spikelets (%)	Plants surviving (%)
0	82.1	98.4
4,500	32.1	46.3
6,000	28.7	17.7
7,500	27.5	6.7
9,000	19.1	1.1
10,500	10.5	0.3
12,000	1.2	0.0

Table 2. Comparison of hybrid seed production methods, Hefei, 2004.

Method	Plants ha ⁻¹ (no. × 1,000)	Effective panicles ha ⁻¹ (no. × 1,000)	Total spikelets panicle ⁻¹ (no.)	Seed set (%)	1,000-grain weight (g)	Yield (t ha ⁻¹)
Conventional (C)	18.5	218	192.2	47.0	22	4.7
Mixed planting (M)	20.0	260	199.4	58.9	22	6.7
Increase (M - C)	1.5	42	7.2	11.9	0	2.0
Increase (%)	8.1	19.3	3.5	25.3	0	42.6

